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The Role Of Vocational And Technical Education In Preparing Youths For Employment In Sokoto State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted on the role of vocational and technical education in preparing youths for employment in Sokoto state, Nigeria. A total sample of 357 was used in which selected for respondents participated in the study. Three questions were raised to guide the study. The study adopted a Cross-sectional design; the data was collected using questionnaires, the data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics. The respondents were randomly selected from three schools respondents were randomly selected from different schools taken as clusters. The study revealed that training in wood work provides youths with the skills to gain wage/self employment. Similarly, the study findings indicated that training in metal work skills welding was an area that prepares youths for self/ wage self-employment. In addition, the study showed that training in electrical engineering was important in preparing youths for employment. Also, The study concludes and recommends that training students in vocational and technical education is very important in preparing them for job market it provides youth with relevant employment skills Therefore, the government should restructure its educational strategies to come up with a strategy which includes more of vocational education than the theoretical based education; there should be massive sensitization of the vocational and technical education to encourage youths to take up the various prospects in vocational and technical education; government should adequately fund vocational and technical education programmes. Lastly it would be essential to ensure that a mechanism of providing small startup capital is put in place to ensure that students who complete their youths with vocational education access this encourage them to startup their own enterprise.

Keywords: Role, Vocational & Technical Education, Preparing, Youths, Employment

INTRODUCTION

Globally, one of the universal challenges affecting the youths is employment. However, one of the major goals of Vocational education is to prepare learners for careers that are based on manual or practical

activities. Traditionally non-academic and totally related to a specific trade, occupation or Vocational and Technical education has been an integral part of national development strategies in many societies. Career and Technical Education (CTE 2019) define technical education as a planned program of courses and learning experiences that begins with exploration of career opinions, supports basic academic and life skills, and enables achievement of high academic standards, leadership, preparation for industry-define work, and advanced and continuing education.

Unemployment is simply the state of not having a job. Unemployment or joblessness occurs when people are without work and are actively seeking for one. Africa is deeply affected with a high rate of unemployment especially among the youth. Africa is now having the most youthful population in the world with the youth covering close to between 60% and 70% of the continents population Cited by Dike (2013). This menace poses great threats to the strength and growth of Africa. Though unemployment is seen manifested all over the world, the case of Africa is very dilapidating to say the least. Paul, F. (2022)

The role of vocational and technical education gives an individual the skills to live and work as a productive citizen in a global society. Vocational education is designed to offer training to improve individual's general proficiency, especially in relation to their present or future occupations Cited. (Musa I.U 2014). One of the viable instruments of tackling unemployment of youth is vocational and technical education owing to its dynamic nature Nwakpa (2022). Vocational and technical education subjects are the forces driving change in the schools, industries and the society. Mechanized farming requires technical skills that could be obtained in vocational and technical schools. The real tests of success of vocational and technical education are the employability of the youths, personal development, opportunities for further education, career development, public acceptance and image which tackle unemployment. Vocational and technical education performs a social function by empowering youths to participate actively in civil society, processes as self-employed people (Abefe-balogun and Nwakpa, n.d).

The large number of youths roaming the streets in Sokoto is a clear evidence on the existence of unemployment in the state. Sokoto state government in its determination to actualize the eight millennium development goals partnered with the MDG's office in the state towards eradicating extreme poverty through provision of employment and self-reliant initiatives (Nura .A. 2017). It was in view of the high level of this that state government decided to empower youth in local government areas of the state. The indigent youths were trained on various vocational skills to enable them start up business and be able to support their families thereby reducing poverty in the society (Nwosu S.N.2011). At school level, the state government encouraged technical institutions and one polytechnic to offer many vocational and technical education courses, to enable students to acquire skills to engage in gainful employment However, little is known on how vocational and technical education is preparing students for employment despite the laudable initiatives of the stat government.

Therefore, this study will focus on examining the role of vocational and technical education in preparing youth for employment in Sokoto state Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

There is no gain saying that, there are many unemployed youths in Sokoto state Nigeria. However, even in the world youths' report argue that youth need to be empowered with skills in order to facilitate their entry in to the labor market (UN,2021). In this context it recommends that training system be put in place to prepare youth for employment to match the changing technologies and global economic requirement. In this regard, Sokoto state government set technical and vocational initiatives to address unemployment against the state, but this is still a social problem in Sokoto state (National Bureau for unemployment Statistics, 2022; Awang et al., 2011). But Sen, (2017) argues that vocational and technical education skills and knowledge through hands-on experience can enhance capability whereby students can be able to make their own choice to lives they have reason to value.

There is little knowledge on how this state initiative encourages vocational and technical education is preparing students for employment. This study therefore seeks to bridge this gap by attempting to

examine the role of vocational and technical education in preparing youths for employment in Sokoto State Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The specific Objectives of this study are to:

1. Examine the role of woodwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.
2. Assess the role of metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria
3. Determine the role of electrical engineering training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised in order to guide the study:

1. What is the role of woodwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.?
2. In what ways the role of metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria?
3. What is the role of electrical engineering training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on role of woodwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on role of metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto state, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on role of electrical engineering training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. This study was conducted in Sokoto State and all the Government technical colleges in Sokoto state Nigeria. The population comprises of all the 5 Senior Secondary Schools Classes SS1 to SS3 of the technical colleges in Sokoto state, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised five thousand eight hundred and eighty (5880) and three hundred an fifty seven (357) sample was used in Vocational and technical students in Sokoto state, Nigeria. (MSTS, 2024).

According to Arat, (2014), a descriptive research design is used when a researcher aims to identify different attributes such as characteristics, frequencies, trends, correlation, and categories. The views of the vocational and technical students and their head of their departments (teachers) will be sought. Quantitative and qualitative approach would be used for getting their perception on the role of vocational and technical education in preparing youth for employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria and the information obtained was presented through statistical methods such as frequency counts of respondents, tabulation, calculation of percentage response and thematic analysis.

A self-constructed questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on the Role of Vocational and Technical Education in Preparing Youths for Employment” (RVTEPYEQ) with the reliability coefficient. Thus, the reliability coefficient of alpha level was used determine the consistency of the result at 0.05 significant level. Inferential statistics of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used in testing formulated null-hypotheses, at 0.05 significant level.

DATA ANALYSES AND RESULTS

Hypothesis One:

Role of woodwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Table 1: One-Way ANOVA showing difference in the opinion of the respondents on the Role of woodwork training in preparing youths for Employment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1742.045	2	871.023	6.707	001	Rejected
Within Groups	48181.217	355	129.869			
Total	49923.262	357				

The study conducted One-way between-groups analysis of variance to explore if there is significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on the woodwork training in preparing youths for Employment by Respondents Category. There was significant difference in the responses of the respondents belonging to different categories: $F(2, 355) = 6.707, p=0.00$. Post-hoc comparisons using the Sheffe’s test indicated that there was significant difference between the opinion of Head of the departments and teachers while students there was no significant difference between the opinion of head of departments and teachers. Based on this, the hypothesis that says; there is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on the vocational and technical education on students of woodwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto state, Nigeria is rejected.

Hypothesis Two:

Role of metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Table2: One-Way ANOVA showing difference in the opinion of the respondents on the role of metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1742.045	3	581.023	6.707	001	Rejected
Within Groups	48181.217	354	129.869			
Total	49923.262	357				

The study conducted One-way between-groups analysis of variance to explore if there is significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on the metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment by Respondents Category. There was significant difference in the responses of the respondents belonging to different categories: $F(2, 354) = 6.707, p=0.00$. Post-hoc comparisons using the Sheffe’s test indicated that there was significant difference between the opinion of H O Ds and Teachers; students and teachers while there was no significant difference between the opinion of H O Ds and teachers. Based on this, the hypothesis that says; there is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on the role of vocational and technical education on metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto state, Nigeria is rejected.

Hypothesis Three:

Role of electrical engineering training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Table 3: One-Way ANOVA showing difference in the opinion of the respondents on the role of electrical engineering training in preparing youths for Employment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	1742.045	2	871.023	6.707	001	Rejected
Within Groups	48181.217	355	129.869			
Total	49923.262	357				

The study conducted One-way between-groups analysis of variance to explore if there is significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on the Role of electrical engineering training in preparing youths for Employment in Respondents Category. There was significant difference in the responses of the respondents belonging to different categories: $F(2, 355) = 6.707, p=0.00$. Post-hoc comparisons using the Sheffe's test indicated that there was significant difference between the opinion of H O Ds and teachers; teachers and students while there was no significant difference between the opinion of H O Ds and teachers. Based on this, the hypothesis that says; there is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents on the role of vocational and technical Education metalwork training in preparing youths for Employment in Sokoto state, Nigeria is rejected.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The hypothesis one sought to know the role of vocational and technical education strategies trained in woodwork. The study revealed that youths improved as a result of strategies of vocational and technical trained in woodwork through regular marking of teacher lesson plan and practical work regularly allowing teachers to participate in the selection of materials for curriculum implementation, engages in classroom visitation and demonstration of new methods of delivering instructions among others. This finding is bias of respondent status because opinion HODs is significantly difference from that of teachers and students ($p.value=0.001$). Tyler (2016) found that the HODs impact is of significance due to the actions that they take to create the school-wide conditions that support student learning, and directly on teacher job creation. Adeniji (2013) study revealed similar findings that HODs provide curriculum and instructional participation to a little extent. In addition, he reported that HODs were found to take actions such as planning with teachers to implement curriculum and further found to facilitate strategies that make for improvement of students' achievement standards and regular supervision. Kolawole (2011) on the other hand, reported that inspectors were alert to the possibilities for improvement of instructions, possess the ability to work and actively engaged in discharging their duties in terms of monitoring and evaluation. Contrary to the above findings, Sale (2016) revealed that that HODs demonstration strategy of learning supervision did not significantly influence teachers on practical work. The contradiction may as result of the scope of the previous study, which only focus on demonstration strategy while the present study exploited all the possible strategies of learning/instructional supervision on much training in practical aspects.. This implies that H O Ds role performance of learning supervision are effectively carried out in the area under study and consequently improve students creativity.

The research question two corresponding hypothesis sought to reveal what characterized H O Ds role in training metalwork prepared and it consequence on youth employment. The study revealed that teacher's job creation improved due to H O D's role for more of practical aspects on training students through application for showing concern for school participation activities, suspension of students that regularly violate school rules and regulation and allowing staff on duty to discipline erring students among others. However, the H O Ds under study show less concern on the roaming about of the people with the school vicinity and this distract both teacher and students during classroom practical activities. This finding is bias of respondent status because opinion H O Ds is significantly difference from that of teachers and students ($p.value=.001$). This finding is similar to report of Uhaa (2017) who found that H O Ds are effective their role of practical aspects in their maintenance of discipline through increased parental involvement, fairness, firmness, punishment and reward, assigning leadership role among staff and students.

CONCLUSION

Inferring from the opinions of the respondents in respect to the role of vocational and technical education in preparing youths for employment in Sokoto State; whereby majority of respondent expressed positive impact of vocational and technical education strategies on youths for employment. The study therefore

concluded that youths for employment largely depends on efficiency and effectiveness of H O D's administrative strategies of instructional supervision on more of practical aspects, disciplinary measures.

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